

DIAGNOSIS AND TREATMENT OF BRAIN MENINGIOMAS

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Introduction. Meningiomas are slow-growing, benign tumors that originate from the meningotheial cells of the brain membranes. They compress the surrounding tissues but do not infiltrate them. Early diagnosis and optimal treatment are of great importance. This study evaluates the effectiveness of diagnostics and surgical treatment of meningiomas.

Purpose of research. Assessment of Brain Meningiomas Based on Modern Diagnostic Techniques and Surgical Treatment Outcomes.

Materials and Methods. The study included 55 patients. Diagnosis was performed using Computed Tomography/Magnetic Resonance Imaging and angiography. Surgical methods included embolization and craniotomy. Postoperative outcomes were assessed through neurological evaluation, imaging studies, and the Karnofsky scale.

Results of Research. The study included 55 patients diagnosed with brain meningiomas. Among them, 65% were women, and 35% were men, with the highest incidence observed in the 40–60 age group (58%). The main symptoms were headache (82%), epileptic seizures (43%), visual impairment (37%), and cognitive dysfunction (29%). The chi-square test results indicated that epileptic seizures and headaches were significantly associated with tumor location ($P < 0.05$). All patients underwent Computed Tomography (100%), Magnetic Resonance Imaging (58%), and angiography (33%). Angiography was primarily performed in patients scheduled for embolization. As a result, the embolized group experienced reduced blood loss and shorter surgery duration ($P < 0.01$). A total of 30 patients underwent embolization before surgery, while 25 patients underwent direct surgery. The operation duration in the embolized group was 3.5 ± 0.6 hours, whereas in the non-embolized group, it was 5.2 ± 0.8 hours ($P < 0.05$). Blood loss was 400 ± 150 ml in the embolized group and 800 ± 250 ml in the non-embolized group ($P < 0.01$). The need for blood transfusion was 5% in the embolized group compared to 36% in the non-embolized group ($P < 0.01$). Postoperative complications were observed in 10% of embolized patients and 32% of non-embolized patients ($P < 0.05$). The hospital stay was 6.2 ± 1.5 days in the embolized group and 9.8 ± 2.1 days in the non-embolized group ($P < 0.05$). Functional recovery was assessed using the Karnofsky Performance Scale. The preoperative score was 70 ± 10 , which improved to 85 ± 8 postoperatively ($P < 0.05$). The embolized group showed better recovery, with a postoperative score of 90 ± 6 ($P < 0.05$). Neurological complications were observed in 16% of patients, infectious complications in 8%, venous thrombosis in 6%, and epileptic syndrome in 5%. Complication rates were lower in the embolized group ($P < 0.05$). Surgical outcomes were evaluated using the Simpson classification. Total tumor resection (Simpson I–II) was achieved in 80% of cases, while subtotal resection (Simpson III–IV) was performed in 20% of cases. Brain meningiomas are most commonly observed in patients aged 40–60, with 65% of cases occurring in women. Embolization before surgery significantly reduced operation duration, blood loss, and the need for transfusion ($P < 0.01$). Postoperative functional recovery improved, particularly in the embolized group ($P < 0.05$). Higher surgical radicality (Simpson I–II) was associated with a lower recurrence risk ($P < 0.05$).

Conclusions. Brain meningiomas are most commonly observed in women aged 40–60

years (65%). Preoperative embolization reduced surgery duration (3.5 hours vs. 5.2 hours, $P < 0.05$), blood loss volume (400 mL vs. 800 mL, $P < 0.01$), transfusion requirements (5% vs. 36%, $P < 0.01$), complication rates (10% vs. 32%, $P < 0.05$), and hospital stay duration (6.2 days vs. 9.8 days, $P < 0.05$), thereby accelerating patient recovery. Complete resection (Simpson I–II) was achieved in 80% of cases, reducing the risk of recurrence. Surgery combined with embolization enhances safety and improves overall outcomes.